

The Relation between Organizational Intelligence and Prerequisites for the Establishment of Learning Organization in I.R.I.B¹ Centers in Provinces

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Abstract

In competitive atmosphere dominating media in the world, all the management systems of media should recognize two important components: Organizational intelligence and learning organization.

The present study was carried out with the view to establishing the relationship between organizational intelligence and prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization in I.R.I.B centers of provinces. Regarding aim, the study is applicable, and methodically it is a descriptive-correlation one. The sample population for the research comprises managers and experts at I.R.I.B centers of provinces and the 265 subjects were selected via random sampling classification. To measure organization intelligence, Albrecht's (2003) 7- dimensional model was used and to assess prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization Denton's (1998) 9-dimentional model was used. The results revealed that the components being: "appetite for change", " knowledge deployment", "shared fate", "alignment and congruence" have respectively highest degree of relation with linear model of "prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization "and using aforementioned components a dependable model can be developed which can explain the 49 percent increase of the strength of variance model related changes of prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization.

Keywords: organizational intelligence; learning organization, broadcast company media management.

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Introduction

Over the recent decades and concurrent with enormous wave of social, economic, political, and cultural changes, organizations have encountered multitude structural and fundamental changes. Considering great ever-changing dynamism in organizations' atmosphere and the advent of new technologies in business and rivals using innovative and creative methods and processes, complexities were created in all working environments. If organizations want to be innovative and creative, they need to feel environmental changes quickly and carefully analyze rivals' and customers' behaviors and take measures to improve their products and business methods. In other words, they should be ever learners; one of the most important tools to achieve this is the establishment of learning organization and institutionalizing learning process in the organizations. As Griffin puts it "When environmental conditions are increasingly and quickly changing: the only competitive advantage possible is learning faster than others. (Zaraee, 2001, pp. 60-61). In other words, for the companies to remain efficient and active despite the ever-increasing rivals' attacks it is required to be flexible and creative and learn continuously. Therefore, it is necessary that the knowledge in organizations, which is their principle asset in the knowledge-oriented economic, be updated ceaselessly. This, in turn, can help organization to fight turbulent atmosphere and tough competitors and guarantee the survival and activity of the organization. It goes without saying, that if learning is not ongoing and continuous, the organizational knowledge is not updated; consequently it will not be valuable for the organization. Additionally, in current era, it is not possible to manage and generate knowledge and use organizational knowledge effectively without employing smart systems. Dixon (1990), believes that learning organization is a response to changing, dynamic and unpredictable working environment. The essence of learning organization is actually exploiting phenomenal capacity of its members, so as to improve the performance which leads to the betterment of organization conditions (Zaraee. et al, 2003, p.49). On the other hand if new organization wants to remain efficient in business they have to consider other kinds of intelligences and use them in their systems. Intelligence has bought about changes in organizations and has modified their business

from conventional and old to modern and new. Besides, there are more changes every day and since smart systems has become a widespread phenomenon in working environment, organizations which fall behind the intelligence movement will be excluded from the game and regress gradually. In other words, employing smart system is not an option but a necessity for survival. Since, businesses are becoming more and more complicated business processes and actions and reactions of rivals also are becoming more and more sophisticated. Using shrewd calculations helps managers to adapt their working conditions with unpredictable cases and reduce their decisions 'risks at different levels specifically organization strategic level. (Eslambuli, 2009, pages 16-17).

As in human world and its turbulent atmosphere people who are more intelligent and enjoy higher intelligent quotient, so is the case with world of organizations, particularly in present era. As the time passes and new technologies and sciences advance, fresh challenges and need emerge that make the management of organizations more challenging and complicated. This concept becomes more significant when we accept that nowadays in organizations, in addition to substantial creative human resources; smart machines play a pivotal role in processes in organizations. More clearly, organizational intelligent in modern organizations today is a combination of active human intelligence and machine intelligence. Undoubtedly, managers are inevitably bound to utilizing these two smart streams, if they want to improve the dynamism and efficiency in their organizations (Elahiyan & Vaziree, 2009, P. 50). Putting it another way, intelligent behavior is not shaped through Logical reasoning, but it depends on the knowledge upon which reasoning is based. (Sadri, 2009, p.28) and knowledge is the result of processed data. Information is transformed to knowledge when it is exploited to increase the efficiency or added value or to create value (Abthi and Solavati 2006,7) and this knowledge creates competitive cutting edge for the organization. (Haml, 1990,79). Karl Albrecht (2002) argues that organizational intelligence is the capacity of an organization to trigger the mental capacities in an organization and rally these capacities to fulfill the mission of the organization. Organizational intelligence is all the required skills for an organization combined which are adaptability with changes, Acting and

reacting fast flexibility and the capacity to renovate. Mutsuda (1992)-one of the developers of organizational theory –claims that organizational intelligence is a combination of human and machine intelligence. Organizational intelligence introduced by Mutsuda integrates the process of human knowledge and machine knowledge to solve problems .He believes organizational intelligence is the capability of an organization to solve an organizational problem.(Taheri-Lari 2010, P.2).Organizational intelligence, through relying on human intelligence carefully recognizes and manages unlimited resource of mental assets and taps them to increase the flexibility of the organization to adapt itself toLocal,national and global needs. Moreover, through providing suitable foundations, it creates the required conditions to generate knowledge and to help organizational learning which in turn improves the innovation and creativity capacities. In other words, if the proper foundations are laid to improve organizational intelligence, organizations also through economical but tactful use of energy and resources facilitate and precipitate the achievement of the goals, means the efficiency and efficacy of productivity are improved. Furthermore, due to increase of adaptability capacity with environment and affecting its surroundings the organization survival is guaranteed.

Organizational intelligence is the capacity of an organization as a whole to increase information, innovation, and public knowledge and to act efficiently based on created knowledge (Macmaster and Michelle 1996, pages 1-9).

Over the past decades there have been numerous studies on different factors such as organizational culture, structure, technology etc. affecting prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization. Some of the researchers believe that organizational intelligence can help to improve the establishment of learning organization because successful reactions of organizations in highly dynamic and hostile business environment of today depends on their capacity to provide necessary information as far as possible. (MalekZadeh, 2009, p.28).

Notwithstanding the foregoing fact, not many surveys have been carried out on the relation of organizational intelligence and prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization. Having said that, if managers concentrate on intelligent capacities, they can perceive environmental

changes more quickly than others and can learn how to adapt themselves to these changes.

Today, media organizations are very complex and provide a fertile ground for surveys worldwide. One the other hand, their role in political social, economic cultural survival of governments, has turned them into one of most important power bases in the society. On the other hand, implementing new and innovative management methods for functioning and efficacy of complicated media organizations have caused more problems for both ever. Mass media is a developing and changing industry which provides job opportunities, generates cultural goods, provides comprehensive public service and it is a supplier in interaction with other various industries. Thus, they need systematic, strategic and futuristic studies more than ever.

Nowadays, mass media specifically TV and radio with unprecedented growth and influence in societies and all aspect of all social life, has turned into dominant origin for all the realization of social realities. Numerous studies have shown that mass media play a pivotal role in cultivating and developing a habit (Farhangi, Sarokhani, Qolipour, Roshandad, & Arbetani, 2007, p. 103). New technologies have made it possible to send messages via TV and radio network beyond geographic borders. Mass media also has tried to attract viewers abroad. That is why broadcasting companies have numerous rivals worldwide. Hence, relying on new tools, in a dynamics and ever changing context, mass media competes with other TV and radio channels and interactive social networks and online radio and TV sites. That is why, in each media management system, establishing a learning organization can be one of the strategies to compete with and fight media. In this line, the overall aim of this research is to find the relation between organizational intelligence and the prerequisite for the establishment of learning organization in I.R.I.B centers in provinces.

Theoretical Foundations

Organizational intelligence is defined as a basic active material or strategic vision to uncover important factors including macro decisions based on business data to properly inform decision making process (Liebowitz, 2009, p. 14). In this study, we take organizational intelligence for organizational capacity. Therefore, organizational

intelligence helps the organization to changes, gather information, prioritize learning and improving, generate knowledge, achieve organizational goals and adapt itself with outside environment in practice. Hence, organizational intelligence basically includes: learning, knowledge, prediction and problem solving. In this research the model for organizational intelligence is Karl Albrecht's model. He also has defined organizational intelligence as “capacities and talents in an organization to mobilize all the mental capacities of an organization and to concentrate them in order to accomplish the defined organizational mission. (Albrecht, 2002. P. 10).

Karl Albrecht model comprises seven dimensions. It is more complete than other models offered: these dimensions are:

- 1- **Strategic Vision:** each organization needs a theory, an organization principle or a definition which it seeks to meet or search for.
- 2- **Share/Common Fate:** a situation in which all or majority of the people in an organization e.g. stakeholders, providers and partners at times the family members of the organization staff, know what is the mission of the organization and realize that they have a common goal and each individual understands the success of the organization.
- 3- **Appetite for change:** in an intelligent organization, it is defined as a change which indicates challenge. A situation for facing new and exciting experiences. Appetite for change presses us for being so great in our strategic vision that we can adopt ourselves with all different kinds of changes.
- 4- **Spirit:** regardless of common fate, this entity comprises the satisfaction to do tasks more than what is needed to meet the standards.
- 5- **Alignment and Congruence:** with the absence of set of rules to fallow, each team will face numerous problems and disagreements while working. Individuals and team should be divided to shoulder responsibilities and take on different tasks so as to accomplish the goals and mission of the organization, and should formulate a set of rules to interact and communicate with each other and the environment.

Knowledge Deployment: nowadays, measures taken in an organization which results in success or failure have been basically based on efficient deployment of knowledge, information and data. The activity in an organization heavily depends on the knowledge acquired and instant decisions made.

Performance Pressure: managers should not only be involved with performance. In an intelligent organization each executive should hold his\her respective position. The leaders could introduce the concept of “executive leverage” and support that. However, the concept is effective when it is defined as a set including reciprocal expectations and operational obligations for mutual success.

Learning Organization

Generally, learning organization is defined as an organization which is adept at generation, acquisition and transference of knowledge to change and modify its behavior. Senge (1990) believes learning organizations are those organizations in which individuals continuously improves their skills in order to achieve the set goals, a context in which new patterns of thoughts are developed collectively and team ideas are introduced and individuals learn how to learn collectively. In other words learning organizations are called knowledge generating organizations. Garvin (1993) maintains that learning organization is an organization that is able to generate, acquire and transfer knowledge and coordinate its behavior which reflects new knowledge and approaches. Horbar (1991) believes that learning organization is an organization that learns over the time and it changes and revolutionizes its performance. Foral and Laylz (1985) also believe that learning organization is an organization that its performances are modified and improved as it is informed and perceives better. (Elahi et.al, 2007, p. 22). Qahremani (2001) maintains that in a learning organization learning low to learn is more important than knowledge, information or learning itself, and innovation and creativity is more valuable than stability and adaptability. (Qahremani, 2001, p. 191. Peddler, et al) believe that a learning organization facilitates learning for all staff and it is continuously revolutionized (Peddler, 2000.p.54). In coo’s perspective learning

organization is identical to scientific organization (Coo, 2001, p.197). Learning organization is an organization in which individuals ceaselessly sharpen their skills so as to accomplish the set goals. It is a context in which new patterns of thoughts are developed, collective thinking is promoted and individuals learn how to learn collectively. So, learning organization is an organization which changes overtime and revolutionizes its performance (Senge, 2005, p.10).

Denton's 9-dimensional model is used to study the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization. The dimensions are as follow:

- 1- **Learning Strategy:** strategy means a plan or a map or an arrangement or a model or a position or an approach. Learning strategy is foundation or structure to implement the idea of learning and supervise an operation that results in organization learning.
- 2- **Flexible Structure:** it is an organizational structure of relations guideline which governs the occupation (Cobines, Mintsburg, and James, 1994, pp.38-40). Organizational structure is a set of guidelines that breaks down the job to specific tasks and coordinates them. One of the conditions for the establishment of learning organization in each organization is the flexibility of the structure of organization.
- 3- **Blame-Free Culture:** culture is a set of moderately homogenous values, beliefs, customs, etiquette and established styles which is shared by staff in an organization. In blame free culture asking is a value and there is no blame for the enquirer while every question, idea, opinion, criticism or suggestion even the wrong ones are warmly welcomed.
- 4- **Common Goal:** Senge (1990) claims that common goal is a power which behaves like a tremendous power and coerce them to act. Common goal is the answer to the question of: "what we are trying to create?" personal goal directs our potential and actual capacity towards a certain target, common goal, in practice, plays the same role at organizational level and consequently generates a tremendous power. The common goal is a goal that most of the members of organization share, because actually they see it as their own personal goals. (ZaraeeMatin, 2003, p. 54-55).
- 5- **External Awareness:** it is a process through which individuals can obtain the required information which is not available in the company outsourcing. In other words, "to what extent and how the environment influences the organization and its staff?"
- 6- **Creation and Transference of Knowledge:** a process through which the organization acquires the necessary skills about learning (institutionalizing knowledge), coding, transferring and disseminating knowledge. (Abtahi & Salavati , 2006, 56).
- 7- **Quality:** quality is the common, mostly-referred-to term whose meaning and application are construed differently. But, what they all have in common is the match between goods or services with customer needs and expectations. Quality is commonly defined as the compatibility of goods with characteristics that customers have in mind or that extent to which customers expectations are met. (Hosseini & Qaderi 2010, p.91).
- 8- **Supportive Atmosphere:** organizational atmosphere is defined as the internal characteristics in an organization which discriminates it form other organizations or influence its personal. Organizational atmosphere is assessed through its staff's descriptions and perceptions. (Halpin and craft cited in Goudarzi & Gaminian, 2002 pp. 40-41).
- 9- **Teamwork:** in the complicated world today, in order to accomplish their goals, organizations need the cooperation and collaboration of their personnel. Teamwork helps the team members to share each other's knowledge and flexible strategies make doing jobs, having different skills, shaping knowledge, and understanding views of team members possible. Moreover, teamwork provides fertile ground for developing new and ambitious ideas and facilitates generating new knowledge (QoorbaniZadeh, 2008, p. 101-103).

Methodology

The present study considering aim is practical and methodologically, it is (descriptive-correlative). The sample population for this research comprises managers, experts, and producers at I.R.I.B centers in provinces. Random sampling classification method or proportion method is

used. So, senior and middle managers, program makers and experts working at I.R.I.B centers in provinces proportionate to the number of them in sample population 265 subjects were selected randomly.

In this study organizational intelligence is independent variable and for measuring it Albrecht's 49-question tested questionnaire according to Likert attitude measuring range with 4 degree being very little, little, much and very much was used.

The independent variable is prerequisites for the establishment of learning organizations for measuring it Denton's 36 question tested questionnaire to Likert's attitude measuring range with 4 degrees being very little, little, much and very much to ensure the validity of the research the quality methods means experts and professionals evaluation, books and papers, Albrecht organizational intelligence questionnaire and Denton's prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization were used. To measure the authenticity of questionnaire experts and professionals views were taken into account. In addition, to test the reliability of the tools, 30 questionnaires were randomly given to 30 subjects out of the sample population and after having been collected the reliability of the data was validated through SPSS, Cronbach's Alpha method. The related coefficient calculated is 77%, the calculated Alpha coefficient for 7 dimensions of Albrecht organizational intelligence model are as follow: strategic vision 0.76; common fate: 0.81; appetite for change 0.77; spirit 0.72; Alignment and Congruence: 0.74 knowledge deployment: 0.83 and performance pressure 0.73.

The calculated Alpha coefficient for the questionnaire related to prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization is 81%.

Furthermore, the coefficient for its respective dimension are as follow: learning strategy 0.83; flexible structure 0.79; blame-free culture 0.84; common goal: 0.79; external awareness: 0.77; knowledge generation and transference 0.86; quality 0.84; organizational atmosphere: 0.73; team work 0.83.

As was mentioned above, considering that all Alpha coefficients calculated are greater than 0.7 and it can be concluded that the questionnaires are reliable enough. It means that the questions are not answered randomly or haphazardly, but they are affected because of the effect of tested variable because, firstly what researcher intended to test was exactly measured and secondly, respondents' inferences were all the same.

Findings

The result related to the variable "organizational intelligence" in I.R.I.B centers provinces in table-1 reveals that the organizational intelligence of the sample population is 2.53 which comparing with 2.5 of theoretical average is above medium. Moreover, "appetite for change: 2.60 is the maximum and "common fate" 2.46 is the minimum.

On the other hand, the results from analysis of related indexes of prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization in I.R.I.B centers-table -2- reveals that the average 2.34 which is lower than theoretical average (2.5) lower than average. Besides, the component "blame-free culture "is 2.56 the maximum and "supportive atmosphere" 1.94 is the minimum.

Table 1: Results of T. test (Organizational Intelligence)

Mean difference	Observed mean	Sig.	df	t	Components
0.02	2.52	0.421	264	0.807	Strategic vision
0.04	2.46	0.165	263	1.193	Common fate
0.10	2.60	0.004	264	2.891	Appetite for change
0.05	2.55	0.131	264	1.515	Spirit
0.02	2.48	0.437	264	0.451	Alignment & congruence
0.09	2.59	0.010	264	2.578	Knowledge deployment
0.04	2.54	0.185	261	1.329	Performance pressure
0.03	2.53	0.199	264	1.287	Organizational intelligence

Table 2: Results of T. test (Establishment of Learning Organization)

Mean difference	Observed mean	Sig.	Df	t	Components
0.08	2.42	0.304	26	-2.262	Learning strategy
0.19	2.31	0.000	26	-4.342	Flexible structure
0.06	2.56	0.143	26	1.468	Blame-free culture
0.07	2.43	0.079	26	-1.762	Common goal
0.47	2.03	0.000	25	-13.117	External awareness
0.17	2.33	0.000	26	-5.400	Creation & transference of knowledge
0.10	2.40	0.022	26	-2.305	Quality
0.56	1.94	0.000	25	-14.308	Support atmosphere
0.22	2.28	0.000	26	-6.769	Teamwork
0.16	2.34	0.000	26	-6.30	Prerequisites for the Establishment of Learning Organization

Spearsman Tests for Correlation between Variables

As mentioned before, one of the aims of this research was to study and test the existence of a meaningful relation between “organization

intelligence” and its components on the hand, and the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization” and its components on the other hand. To achieve this, the results of Spearman correlation coefficient among variables were studied.

Testing the Principle Hypothesis

H0: There is meaningful relation between “organizational intelligence” and “the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization” in I.R.I.B centers in provinces.

H1: There is not a meaningful relation between “organizational intelligence” and “the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization in I.R.I.B centers in provinces.

The results of Spearman table-4- show that there relation between the variables “organizational intelligence” and “the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization” in I.R.I.B centers in provinces is meaningful (sig= 0.0000 and $r= 0.783$) which is approximately 0.78. This in turn, shows a direct and strong correlation. In other words, null hypothesis is rejected and the opposite is proved valid.

Regression Test Analysis

since simple correlation test only measures simple linear correlation between one variable with another variable, in this study researchers have utilized a multiple, linear regression test to evaluate the effect of organizational intelligence components on prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization and have develop a reliable model so as to predict the extent of availability of prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization according to the data related to organizational intelligence and its components. Through regression analysis it is possible to predict the related changes via independent variable and to determine the share of each which causes such changes.

In order to calculate the error rate of the prediction for the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization in I.R.I.B centers in provinces according to organizational intelligence components, all the 7 dimensions were analyzed step by step using regression model. The results which will be elaborated on later, revealed that “appetite for change”, “knowledge deployment” “shared fate”, “alignment and congruence” have

had the greatest influence on “prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization” respectively are employing the very same component it is feasible to develop a reliable model. The three left out components being “strategic vision”, “spirit” and “performance pressure were not taken into account due to their negligible effect.”

Step by Step Regression Analysis

Step 1

In the step first the variable entering the calculation is “the appetite for change” which has the greatest influence ($R=0.632$, $R^2 = 0.397$) on the dependent variable and calculated **F** resultant from variance analysis (sig=0.000 and $F=171.018$) has been meaningful and reliable therefore, “appetite for change” alone could cause 40% of change on dependent variable “The prerequisite for the establishment of learning organization.”

Step 2

In this step “knowledge deployment” entered the equation the results for coefficient correlation were ($R=0.674$, $R^2= 0.454$, $R^2AD= 0.450$) and the resultant **F** from variance analysis was (sig=0.000, $F=106.573$) so the model is dependable. Therefore “appetite for change” and “knowledge deployment” cause about 45% of the changes on dependent variable being “the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization”. Actually “knowledge deployment” add 5 more percent to the power of model.

Step 3

In this step “common fate” entered the question. The resultant coefficient correlation was ($R=0.690$, $R^2=0.476$, $R^2AD=0.470$) and the calculated **F** from variance analysis was (sig=0.000, $F= 77.178$) which was meaningful and the model was reliable. So far, “appetite for change”, “knowledge deployment” and “common fate” came up to 47% of changes for dependent variable being “the prerequisite for the establishment of learning organization”. It actually added 2 more percent to the power of model.”

Step 4

In this step “alignment and congruence” entered the equation. The resultant coefficient correlation was ($R=0.701$, $R^2=0.491$, $R^2AD=0.483$) and the resultant **F** from variance analysis was (sig=0.000, $f=61.346$) which was meaningful and the mode was dependable. All the 4 components combined cause 49 percent of changes on dependable variable being “the prerequisites for the

establishment of learning organization.” Actually
 “alignment and congruence add 2 more percent to

the power of model.”

Table 3: Results of Step by Step Regression Analysis)

Variance inflation factor	Tolerance indicator	Sig.	t	Beta	Estimate error	Coefficients estimate	Variable entered to equation	Steps
1.000	1.000	0.000	6.291		0.123	0.772	Fixed sum	1
		0.000	13.080	0.632	0.046	0.601	Appetite for change	
1.982	0.505	0.000	4.265		0.126	0.537	Fixed sum	2
		0.000	6.162	0.400	0.062	0.381	Appetite for change	
1.982	0.505	0.000	5.065	0.329	0.062	0.312	Knowledge deployment	
2.398	0.417	0.004	2.917		0.132	0.386	Fixed sum	3
		0.000	4.355	0.306	0.067	0.291	Appetite for change	
2.110	0.474	0.000	4.202	0.277	0.062	0.262	Knowledge deployment	
1.860	0.535	0.001	3.239	0.201	0.065	0.210	Common fate	
2.442	0.410	0.031	2.169		0.135	0.292	Fixed sum	4
		0.000	4.000	0.280	0.067	0.262	Appetite for change	
2.398	0.410	0.003	3.028	0.210	0.066	0.199	Knowledge deployment	
1.892	0.528	0.003	2.953	0.182	0.064	0.190	Common fate	
1.652	0.605	0.006	2.781	0.160	0.054	0.149	Alignment & congruence	

Discussion and Conclusion

According to coefficient of partial correlation “appetite for change” has the greatest partial correlation 0.397 with prerequisites for the establishment of learning organization” than the other components of organizational intelligence do. It means “the appetite for change” component

is an appropriate identifier for “the establishment of learning organization and to improve the favorable condition this component can be used. It means through encouraging employees for change, growth and compatibility, strategies to support innovations, encouraging employees to work out more efficient ways to do tasks, giving the chance to ask questions about conventional ways to do tasks, keeping the red tapes to a

minimal ,managers admitting their mistakes, providing welcoming atmosphere, accepting an idea or behavior which is Avant-guard for an organization or public, the need for learning more is created and the ways to handle tasks is improved significantly. All these, in turn, make the employee to be permanent learners so as to do the jobs better and produce premium products. In such climate learning is institutionalized in the organization and consequently the organization is more prepared to become a learning organization. Furthermore, subsequent components that entered the regression equation at 2nd, 3rd and 4th steps are “generation and deployment of knowledge”, “common fate”, “alignment and congruence.”

Prioritizing generation and development of knowledge helps employees to seek and acquire useful knowledge for the organization relentlessly, and in addition to acquiring knowledge, they share this knowledge with other members of the organization. This, in turn, improves the organizational knowledge. In the ambient where imparting and generating knowledge is valuable so are learning and teaching. This kind of organization is a learning organization. Taking into account “the common fate” means believing that the members of the organization are analogous to the members of a family who are aboard a ship in the middle of the sea. Any threat to the organization is a threat for each member of the organization and opportunities ahead for organization if exploited would be beneficial for all the members. Considering this fact is a reason that the experts and managers of the organization continuously search to spot the weaknesses strengths of the organization, counter threats and take advantage of new opportunities for the organization. Considering the situation, paying attention to “the common fate” prioritizes learning in order to improve the future from which everyone has a share. Taking into account “alignment and congruence” helps the structure of the organization to suit the organization mission. Moreover, the goals in each department are set in a manner that instead of provoking disagreement helps cooperation and coordination. In such organization individual and team goals are in agreement with those of organization and working with such organization institutionalizes teamwork. Under such conditions employees in working team usually try to accomplish the company’s goals, and they learn more effective ways to do jobs. Concluding from what went on, it can be

said that using step by step multiple regression equation, the principle hypotheses is conformed.

Suggestions

- 1- According to research findings and the positive effect of organizational intelligence on the prerequisites of the establishment of learning organization, it is suggested to the experts and managers of I.R.I.B centers in provinces that through running training courses lay that necessary ground to help their staff learn about the concept of organization intelligence and prerequisites of the establishment of learning organization.
- 2- According to the findings, the most effective components of organizational intelligence on the prerequisites for the establishment of learning organizations are: “appetite for change”-“deployment and development of knowledge”-“common fate”, alignment and congruence. Therefore, it is suggested that the managers and experts of I.R.I.B centers in provinces take them into account.
- 3- The findings revealed that currently in I.R.I.B centers in provinces the conditions are not favorable for the establishment on learning organization. Further research on the effective factors for the establishment of learning organization and its respective impediments to accomplish this in the foregoing organization is recommended to future researchers.

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